

IPBES invasive alien species assessment, data management report for Chapter 3. Section 3.2.1: Socio-cultural drivers and social values

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Description

Section 3.2.1 assesses the role of sociocultural drivers and social values as drivers of biological invasions. The experts conducted a systematic review to report on the existing knowledge on this driver. This systematic review consists in the main source of evidence for the section.

Process overview

Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** literature review

- **Search language(s):** English

- **Search terms:**

#1 TS=(((invesi* OR alien) OR feral OR exotic) AND species)

#2 TS=(soci* AND value*)

#3 TS=Driver*

#4 TS=review*

- **Search engine:** Web of Science

- **Date:** December 2020

- **Searched time period:** 2000-2019

- **Overview of the search results and selection criteria:**

Number of search result:

#1 TS=(((invesi* OR alien) OR feral OR exotic) AND species), N=26,305

#2 TS=(soci* AND value*) , N=243,870

#3 TS=Driver*, N=141,920

#4 TS=review*, N=2,025,647

#1 AND #2, N=247

#1 AND #2 AND #3, N=13

#1 AND #2 AND #3 AND #4, N=2

Selection criteria:

Search 1: Searched with above terms, then refined by document type (review) excluding low relevant papers by experts' knowledge.

Search 2: Searched with above terms with timespan of 2000 to 2019, then excluded low relevant papers from Top 50 papers by experts' knowledge.

Search 3: Searched with above terms with timespan of 2000 to 2019, then excluded low relevant papers by experts' knowledge.

Number of added papers (experts' knowledge and reviewers' recommendations): 11

- **Step by step analysis (methodology, categories, etc.):**

Number of papers reviewed: 26 (See Chapter 3_literature_review_masterdatabase.xlsx)

Fields extracted:

- Publication title

- Year of publication

- Invasion stage [Uptake and transport; Introduction; Establishment; Spread]

- Biomes [Terrestrial; Freshwater; Marine]

- Taxon [Plant; Vertebrate; Invertebrate; Microbes]

- Type of study [Primary study; Review; Meta-analysis]

- Region [Europe and Central Asia; Asia-Pacific; Oceania; Americas; Africa]

- Unit of analysis [IPBES units of analysis]

-Cross-cutting theme [Scenarios and models; indigenous and local knowledge; Good quality of life]

-Comment (free text)

- **Files (code, review templates, etc.):**

Chapter 3_literature_review_masterdatabase.xlsx